

DIAGNOSTICS OF SOCIAL COMPETENCE IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the current topic of diagnostics of social competence in preschool children. It examines key aspects of assessing the social development of a child at preschool age. The article is intended for a wide range of specialists working with preschool children: teachers, psychologists, parents, and also highlights the importance of diagnostics of social competence, criteria and indicators for assessing diagnostic methods and tools, as well as issues of diagnostic problems.

Introduction. Social competence is one of the key indicators of the personal development of preschool-aged children. It reflects a child's ability to effectively interact with others, understand social norms and rules, and regulate their behavior. Assessing the development levels of social competence allows us to evaluate the results of educational work and determine individual educational paths for each child.

In the current context of preschool education, systematic and comprehensive assessment of children's social competence at different age stages is of great importance. This makes it possible to identify the dynamics of its development, promptly adjust the pedagogical process, and ensure its individualization.

This article examines the specifics of assessing social competence in preschool children across different age groups, analyzes the criteria and indicators for its assessment, and presents the experience of implementing assessment work in preschool educational institutions in Uzbekistan.

Social competence is viewed as an integrative personal quality that includes the following main components:

- cognitive (knowledge of social norms, rules, and methods of interaction);
- Emotional and motivational (ability to empathize, cooperate, and self-regulate);
- Behavioral (ability to apply social knowledge and skills in real-life situations) [1, pp. 36-38].

The assessment of social competence should be aimed at a comprehensive assessment of these components, which will provide a holistic view of the child's social development.

The following criteria and indicators are used to assess the levels of social competence in preschool children:

Criteria and indicators for assessing social competence in preschool children:

- Cognitive;
- Emotional and motivational;
- Behavioral.

These criteria and indicators reflect the complex nature of social competence, encompassing cognitive, emotional and motivational, and behavioral aspects [2, pp. 54-55].

The following methods can be used to study the development levels of social competence in preschool-age children:

- observation of children's behavior in various social interaction situations;
- conversations aimed at identifying social knowledge and understanding;
- analysis of children's creative work (drawings, crafts on social topics);
- problem-solving that models social behavior;
- expert assessments by teachers and parents [3, pp. 85-87].

A combination of methods ensures a comprehensive and objective assessment of children's social competence.

In the younger group of a preschool institution, the primary focus of social competence assessment is on:

- assessing the child's mastery of basic social norms and rules of behavior (communication culture, self-care, interaction with peers);
- identifying the characteristics of children's emotional manifestations and reactions in various social interaction situations;
- determining the level of development of children's basic cooperation and mutual assistance skills [4, pp. 72-74].

In the middle group, social competence assessment involves:

- determining the completeness and depth of children's knowledge of social norms, rules, and modes of interaction;
- assessing children's ability to self-control and self-regulate behavior in accordance with social standards;
- identifying children's ability to establish and maintain positive relationships with peers and adults [5, pp. 83-85].

Methods used: observation, conversations, problem-solving.

In the senior group, social competence assessment focuses on:

- assessing the completeness and awareness of children's social knowledge and their ability to transfer it to practical activities;
- determining the level of development of empathy, compassion, and the desire to help peers;
- identifying children's ability to resolve conflict situations and find compromise solutions [6, pp. 92-94].

Methods used: observation, conversations, problem-solving, expert assessments.

In the preparatory group, social competence assessment is aimed at:

- determining the development of children's generalized social knowledge and concepts;
- assessing children's ability to self-regulate behavior and demonstrate initiative in social interactions;

- identifying children's ability to align their behavior with social norms and rules and demonstrate leadership qualities [7, pp. 100-102].

Methods used: observation, conversations, problem-solving, and expert assessments.

In preschool educational institutions in Uzbekistan, social competence assessments are carried out in accordance with the requirements of State Educational Standards.

Our study showed that teachers use a variety of assessment methods, combining observation, conversations, analysis of children's activities, problem-solving, and expert assessments. This allows for a comprehensive assessment of children's levels of social competence in accordance with age-specific characteristics [8, pp. 77-79].

The assessment results form the basis for planning individual work with children and developing and implementing educational programs aimed at developing their social competence. At the same time, some educators note the need to further refine diagnostic tools and increase competence in their application [9, pp. 90-92].

Thus, the assessment of social competence in preschool children in Uzbekistan is carried out in accordance with the requirements of state educational standards. Its systematic implementation ensures the effectiveness of the process of developing social competence in preschool students.

Conclusion. The assessment of social competence in preschool children is an important component of educational work aimed at its development. It allows us to identify the child's initial level of social development, track the dynamics of its changes, and determine optimal methods and tools.

Criteria covering cognitive, emotional-motivational, and behavioral components are used to assess the development levels of children's social competence. The assessment involves the use of a range of methods, including observation, interviews, analysis of activity products, problem-solving, and expert assessments.

The analysis showed that in preschool educational institutions in Uzbekistan, the assessment of children's social competence is carried out in accordance with state standards. Teachers use a variety of diagnostic methods, ensuring a comprehensive and objective assessment. The diagnostic results become the basis for planning individual work and developing effective educational programs.

Recommendations:

1. Include topics related to improving diagnostic tools and methods for assessing children's social competence in preschool teacher training programs.

2. Develop and implement a unified diagnostic toolkit for assessing children's social competence at different age levels in preschool institutions in Uzbekistan.

3. Ensure active parental involvement in assessing children's social competence using interactive methods.

4. Create a database of diagnostic methods in preschool institutions to track the development of students' social competence.

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